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NEW MODELS OF CARE. REINVENTING HEALTHCARE: WHY, WHAT, HOW

ABSTRACT BOOK

Climate Change Malady as an Inspiration for Healthcare Sector – “Reinventing” Healthy Energy Choices

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Short Paper

Climate change malady had united decision-makers, politicians and most diverse countries in their pursuit in preserving health and solving climate change process. Climate Summit in Paris COP21 in 2015. was not only an important but truly historical moment, where we saw that most decision makers, even they are not health professionals, directly or indirectly argued that climate change is practically and ethically essential to caring about public health.

According the evidence based data, climate change malady, resulting with rise in morbidity and mortality from different diseases. Beside morbidity and mortality climate change produce rise of absenteeism and health costs, also.

In our mission to preserve health, as health professionals, we have to persist in raising our voice for healthy energy combating climate change. Health Professionals, among other professionals, have a unique role in action for healthy energy.

Healthcare sector for its achievements and goals (to help individual and population becoming healthier, to manage different diseases...) but through its requirements and needs (a lot of medical and managerial knowledge and skills, equipment, consumables...) have become a major economy factor. More than that, healthcare sector requires a lot of energy for power generation, heating, lighting, electrical equipment, transport, supplies, ventilation, air conditioning and all other professional activities, which is combination knowledge, skills and energy needs. It was roughly estimated that EU hospitals responsible for 5% of the carbon dioxide emissions annually. The health professionals and health sector as whole have a considerable carbon footprint.

All countries in EU and wider should focus more attention in areas such as energy efficient buildings, renewable heating, cooling and transport in healthcare. Healthcare sectors should be persistent and united in their efforts to find win-win models which includes patient care and sustainable and healthy energy choices at the national and local levels.

Climate change is resulting in changing human resources needs in health sector, more equipment and consumables, better preparedness, smart organization and work on resiliency of health sector in future. But health professionals should give also an example within the sector by their own endeavor and behaviour that reduction of GHG footprint is possible.

One of the most important steps in that process is rethinking our priorities and needs at individual and professional level. Patient safety and care must stay the main goal, but also including advocacy for environmental health, ecologically sustainable healthcare, and high standards in energy efficiency.

"Reinventing" healthcare because of climate change malady is a big challenge and process. It needs help from other professions but we have to persist in our efforts to include topic on healthy energy into education of all health professionals in order to change our attitude in professional life and quality standards of health organizations.